

Components of Islamic Education

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to find out the components of Islamic education. This research uses research methodology of library research data through documents or literature materials in the form of books, magazines, historical stories, etc. The result of this study is that the components in the Islamic education system are very diverse ranging from goals, educators, learners, methods, materials and educational environments. Islamic education requires these components in supporting the learning process and each component is interrelated with each other.

INTRODUCTION

Education is very important for humans in living and managing various lives in the world. Because humans really need various sciences as one of the foundations in living life. Education has the aim of shaping humans into a fully independent person, understanding and practicing educational values in everyday life. (Firmansyah, n.d.)

Education is also a system that contains aspects of vision, mission, goals, curriculum, teaching materials, teaching and learning processes, teachers, students, management, infrastructure advice, costs, environment, and so on. The various components of education form a system that has a distinctive construction or building. In order for the construction foundation of educational buildings to be strong and sturdy, it must have a strong foundation that supports and supports it, so that the educational concept building can stand firmly and can be used as a reference in educational practice.

Education in Islam is a series of processes of empowering humans towards maturity, both intellectually, mentally and morally, to carry out the function of humanity carried out as a servant before his Khaliq and also as Khalifatu fil ardh (preserver) in this universe. Thus, the main function of education is to prepare the next generation) with the abilities and expertise (skills) needed to have the ability and readiness to plunge into the community environment armed with the Qur'an and As-Sunnah.

Islamic education is certainly needed by the Muslim community, because Islam is a clear teaching and religion that is a guide for those based on the Qur'an and its Sunnah. In Indonesia itself, education based on Islam has been established, for example public schools that contain PAI lessons, in madrassas that make the main foundation in their lessons, and pesantren that really teach based on the books of Muslims as guidelines. Not only these institutions, but now there are higher education institutions based on Islamic religious studies.

Understanding Islamic Education

Education in its sense is an attempt to "age" humans or make people know how true their identity and nature as humans are. Through education, humans can grow and develop naturally, whether developing their abilities, knowledge or mentality. Thus, the human being can carry out his duties as a human being.

This also applies to Muslims who have been guided by the Prophet (peace be upon him) by his Islamic teachings. So that it can know the meaning of the creation of humans, and what must be done in carrying out their lives on this earth. So Islamic education is very important for Muslims and can also understand its teachings well.

There are several understandings by experts about the meaning of Islamic education, these definitions include:

Muhammad Fadhil al-Jamali put forward the notion of Islamic education; Efforts to develop, encourage and invite humans to develop based on high and noble life values, so that a more perfect human being is formed.

Omar Muhammad Al-Thoumy al-Syaibany argues that Islamic Education is a process of changing the behavior of individual students in personal life, society and the environment.

Hasan Langgulung formulated Islamic education as a process of preparing the younger generation to fill roles, transfer Islamic knowledge and values that are aligned with human functions to do charity in the world and reap the rewards in the Hereafter.

Muhaimin defined Islamic education by; education is understood and developed from the fundamental teachings and values contained in the Quran and al-Sunnah.

Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that Islamic education is an educational system based on Islamic teachings that covers all aspects of human life needs as servants of Allah, and at the same time becomes a guide for the life of the world and the hereafter.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

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METHODOLOGY

The research methodology used by the author is; type of research approach literature study (library Research). Literature research is a study used in collecting information and data through documents or library materials or

literature in the form of books, magazines, historical stories, etc. Literature study research is carried out in research to solve a problem that is based on a critical and in-depth review of relevant library materials. (Mubtadi, 2011)

Library materials in the form of books, journals, and so on are positioned as a source of ideas or inspiration that can generate ideas and thoughts. This literature study method is used to compile and describe the components of the ideal implementation of Islamic education in Indonesia. The steps in the literature research from Mirzaqon are as follows: (Dwi Cahyono, 2020)

1. Topic selection
2. Exploration of information
3. Determine the focus of research
4. Data source collection
5. Preparation of data presentation
6. Report preparation

The source of data that becomes material is in the form of journals and / or internet sites related to the topic that has been chosen. In this analysis, the process of selecting, comparing, combining and sorting out various understandings will be carried out until relevant ones are found.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Components of Islamic Education

Islamic education has a very broad scope or there is everything related to Islamic education. This can be seen from many aspects or components that are involved either directly or indirectly. These components are the main elements that are very important so as to make the process of Islamic education run smoothly and effectively to achieve the goals of Islamic Education itself. the unity of the components of Isam education, each of which stands alone but is interrelated with each other. (Juwariyah, 2009) The components involved in Islamic education are as follows:

Objectives of Islamic Education

One of the most important and fundamental components in education is the purpose of education. Formulating educational objectives is a mandatory requirement in defining education itself which is at least based on basic concepts about humans, nature, and science and with various considerations of basic principles. This is because education is the most important thing in shaping humans according to what they want.

The purpose of Islamic education is inseparable from the purpose of human life in Islam, which is to create a personal servant of Allah who always fears Him, and can achieve a happy life in the world and hereafter. The goal consists of three aspects, namely faith, science and charity by cultivating and developing and forming positive attitudes, discipline and love for religion in various lives that will later become people who are devoted to Allah SWT. The purpose of human life in Islam is what can be used as the ultimate goal of Islamic education.

specifically more specifically explain what is to be achieved through Islamic education. It is more practical, so that the concept of Islamic education is not just an idealization of Islamic teachings in the field of education. Because it fosters

and fosters religious skills in life and can understand and live the teachings of Islam deeply and thoroughly and with this goal framework formulated expectations to be achieved in certain stages of the educational process, as well as can also be assessed the results that have been achieved. (Rahmat Hidayat, 2016)

According to Hasan langgulung, that the purpose of education in Islam is the same as the purpose of human life created for life on earth. These objectives include:

- Fostering the younger generation to worship Allah Almighty and carry out all his commandments and stay away from his prohibitions.
- Educating the younger generation to be able to live in society by recognizing the principles of cooperation, brotherhood and equality (ukhwah).
- Educating young people to use their minds carefully, creatively, and productively.
- Form a person who likes to open and interact with others, and stay away from being arrogant and aloof.
- Educating the younger generation by using various scientific (rational) thoughts.

Educators

Every educational institution needs professional teachers / teachers, who will ensure the continuity of the teaching and learning process continuously. A good teacher is a teacher who knows how to position himself as a professional in accordance with the needs of an increasingly strong and changing society, as well as the development of the current times. Similarly, it can be said that the responsibility of the teacher is to ensure the success of students in learning where he teaches.

In the Islamic perspective, a teacher must not only be a teacher, but also an educator. Therefore, a person can become a teacher not only because he has met scientific and academic qualifications, but more importantly he must be commendable. Thus, a teacher not only teaches sciences, but more importantly also shapes the character and personality of his students with Islamic morals and teachings. (Rahmat Hidayat, 2016)

Learners

Students are people who study in educational institutions, can also be called students, students or students. How Islam obliges and glorifies those who seek knowledge is reflected in the words of Allah. Among other things, in this verse it is explained that studying is almost as much a position as fighting for the religion of God:

وما كان المؤمنون لينفروا كافة فلولا نفر من كل فرقة منهم طائفة

ليتفقها في الدين ولينذروا قومهم إذا رجعوا إليهم لعلهم يحذرون) : التوبة

(122

"It is clear that all the mu'mins should go to the battlefield. Why not set out a group from each faction to deepen their religious knowledge so that they can give a warning (lesson) to their people when they return. Hopefully they (his people) are alert" (QS. At Taubah: 122)

Students also have the obligation to give respect, appreciation, and as well as good and polite treatment to educators, it is the right of an educator to obtain it all from students. (Mawaddah, 2022) (Rahmat Hidayat, 2016)

Methods In Islamic Education

Broadly speaking, there are five methods in Islamic education, namely:

1) Exemplary Method (Uswah Hasanah)

This method students see and witness, which can be a direct picture of the example of 'uswah hasanah from parents, educators, or people who become role models, so that students can carry out better and easier.

2) Habituation Method

In everyday life, there are things that must be carried out or done either routinely, or not routinely. In carrying out things, tasks, obligations that are routine, it is necessary to apply to students is habituation.

3) Advice Method

The advice method is an old method that is often used by parents, educators, and students by providing advice that builds students for the better.

4) Methods of Paying Attention

This method is usually in the form of praise and appreciation. So that students are happy and can carry out what should be done and what should be left behind

5) Punishment Methods

This method is used only when forced to, meaning that if we have done various methods, but students still do not obey, then the only way is to give punishment, which is punishment that is giving lessons.

Institutional In Islamic Education

In the education system, there is one thing that cannot be separated, namely educational institutions. An educational institution is an institution or institution that oversees, organizes, and implements an educational system in an organized and organized manner to achieve a certain goal in education. (Mawaddah, 2022)

Evaluation

In a broad sense, evaluation is an effort to plan, obtain, and provide information that is indispensable for making alternative decisions. Every activity will definitely be evaluated or assessed by educators and is a process that is

deliberately planned to obtain information or data whether the learning process is successful. In Islamic education, evaluation is one component of the education system that must be carried out systematically and planned as a tool to measure the success or targets to be achieved in the Islamic education process and learning process. (Akhyak, 2021)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Islamic education is an educational system based on Islamic teachings that covers all aspects of human life needs as servants of Allah, and at the same time becomes a guide for the life of the world and the hereafter. Islamic education has a very broad scope and is related to each other related and part of the components of Islamic education.

The components in the Islamic education system are also very diverse ranging from objectives, educators, learners, methods, institutions, and evaluation. In this case, Islamic education requires these components in supporting the learning process in their respective education.

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